

Study of Corrosion Inhibition Property of Polyhydric Alcohols in Relation to their Adsorption Properties

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Manuscript received 8 May 1986, revised 3 June 1987, accepted 11 August 1987

Some polyhydric alcohols have been investigated as surface active and corrosion inhibitive species in mild steel - 1 N sulphuric acid solution system at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The adsorption characteristics of these compounds have been determined by a capillary electrometer; and dependence of the adsorption on structure and concentration of the adsorbate and on potential and charge at the mercury - solution interface has been discussed. The interrelationship between the electrocapillary properties of the compounds and their inhibitive efficiencies in acid corrosion of mild steel have been studied in the light of phi-potential theory.

PHI-potential theory¹ is based on the assumption that in inhibitor problems, comparison of surface activity of a species as evaluated from its electrocapillary characteristics with its inhibitive property, is valid only at potential equidistant from the p.z.c. of a metal; and this has been suggested as a basis to compare the adsorption of inhibitors to different metals². Moreover, it appeared that the parallelism between the surface activity of nitrogen containing organic compounds and lower monohydric alcohols on mercury and their inhibition efficiency in acid corrosion of iron manifest itself also in the similar dependence of these two properties on structure of organic compounds³⁻⁷. The present investigation deals with a systematic study of polyhydric alcohols as surface active and corrosion inhibitive agents in corrosion of mild steels in 1 N sulphuric acid solution at $25 \pm 0.5^\circ$.

Experimental

All corrosion and electrocapillary measurements were carried out using the same acid-inhibitor mixture for the evaluation of K , the inhibition coefficient and $\Delta\gamma$, the depression in surface tension on Hg/H₂SO₄ (1N) interface, as described in the previous communication⁷. Data for the electrocapillary measurements of some typical polyhydric alcohols (*vide* Discussion) in 1 N sulphuric acid solution are presented in Figs. 1 and 2. The decrease in the rate of corrosion observed in the presence of alcohols satisfies fairly well the empirical equation⁸,

$$\log K = \text{Const}_K + \beta_K \log C \quad (1)$$

where, Const_K and β_K are constants typical of a given compound and C is the volume concentration

Fig. 1. Electrocapillary curves for tetramethylene glycol (polar) at different molar concentrations in 1N H₂SO₄ solution: (1) 0.00, (2) 0.5, (3) 1.0, (4) 2.0, (5) 3.0 and (6) 5.0 M. (The electrocapillary curves for polyols sl. nos. 2 and 3, Table 1, were found to follow the same trend).

Fig 2. Electrocapillary curves for glycerol (non-polar) at different molar concentrations in 1N H₂SO₄ solution: (1) 0.00, (2) 2.50, (3) 4.00, (4) 5.625, (5) 7.50 and (6) 10.00 M. (The electrocapillary curves for polyols sl. nos 1, 6-8, Table 1 were found to follow the same trend).

of the additive. At the phi-potential of Hg equal to $\phi = -0.26$ V, which is the mean value of the corrosion potential of Fe in 1 N H₂SO₄ solution in 'phi-scale' (represented by Fe⁰C by dotted line in Fig. 1), nearly all experimental points of the electrocapillary curves (e.c.c.) may be described by the equation²,

$$\log \Delta\gamma = \text{Const}_\gamma + \beta_\gamma \log C \quad (2)$$

where, Const_γ and β_γ are constants specified for a given compound at the given value (-0.26 V) of phi-potential. The values of Const_κ, β_κ, Const_γ and β_γ, calculated from the plot of log K vs log C and from the plot of log Δγ vs log C at Fe⁰C = -0.26 V described earlier⁷ are included in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VALUES OF CONSTANTS OF EQUATIONS (1) AND (2) Fe⁰C = -0.26 V

Sl. no.	Compd.	β _κ	Const _κ	β _γ	Const _γ
1.	Ethylene glycol	0.345	-0.091	0.540	0.850
2.	Propylene glycol*	0.600	-0.220	0.533	1.080
3.	1,3-Butylene glycol*	0.313	-0.009	0.321	1.345
4.	Tetramethylene glycol*	0.350	-0.005	0.340	1.353
5.	Glycerol	0.730	-0.280	0.532	0.938
6.	Erythritol	0.059	+0.026	0.552	0.920
7.	Mannitol	0.180	+0.044	0.614	1.034
8.	Sorbitol	0.103	+0.034	0.528	1.298

TABLE 2—VALUES OF INHIBITION COEFFICIENTS (K) AND SURFACE TENSION DEPRESSION (Δγ; AT Fe⁰C = -0.26 V) AT VARIOUS CONCENTRATIONS (C) OF THE INHIBITORS

C, M (Δγ, dynes cm ⁻¹)	C, M, (K, expt.)	(K, theor.)*	Deviation (±%) from theoretical value
Ethylene glycol			
0.75 (5.50)	1.0 (1.070)		Abnormal Here β _κ ≠ β _γ (refer Table 1)
1.50 (9.50)	2.0 (1.114)		
3.00 (12.00)	3.0 (1.224)		
4.00 (14.00)	4.0 (1.321)		
5.00 (17.75)	5.0 (1.419)		
Propylene glycol			
0.75 (10.00)	2.0 (1.170)	0.870	34.4
1.50 (14.00)	3.0 (1.254)	1.081	13.8
3.00 (20.50)	4.0 (1.379)	1.285	6.9
4.00 (24.25)	4.5 (1.459)	1.343	8.6
5.00 (26.25)	5.0 (1.580)	1.413	11.8
1,3-Butylene glycol			
1.0 (22.25)	1.0 (1.107)	1.109	-0.18
2.0 (30.00)	2.0 (1.256)	1.386	-9.40
3.0 (32.00)	3.0 (1.352)	1.542	-12.4
4.0 (34.25)	4.0 (1.490)	1.730	-13.9
5.0 (35.75)	4.5 (1.654)	1.795	-7.9
-	5.0 (1.944)	1.858	4.6
Tetramethylene glycol			
0.5 (18.00)	1.0 (1.192)	1.130	5.5
1.0 (23.50)	2.0 (1.287)	1.430	-10.0
2.0 (29.25)	3.0 (1.435)	1.641	-12.5
3.0 (32.75)	4.0 (1.570)	1.807	-13.1
5.0 (36.25)	4.5 (1.772)	1.884	-5.9
-	5.0 (1.909)	1.953	-2.2
Glycerol			
2.50 (13.75)	1.0 (1.136)		Abnormal β _κ ≠ β _γ
4.00 (18.00)	2.0 (1.237)		
5.63 (21.75)	4.0 (1.485)		
7.50 (24.25)	6.0 (1.945)		
10.00 (29.50)	8.0 (2.444)		
-	10.0 (2.801)		
Erythritol			
0.50 (6.00)	0.5 (1.023)		Abnormal β _κ ≠ β _γ
1.00 (8.75)	0.8 (1.043)		
1.50 (11.25)	1.0 (1.068)		
2.00 (13.25)	-		
Mannitol			
0.15 (3.50)	0.56 (1.002)		Abnormal β _κ ≠ β _γ
0.30 (4.50)	0.72 (1.030)		
0.45 (6.50)	0.80 (1.059)		
0.60 (8.25)	-		
Sorbitol			
0.11 (5.50)	0.27 (1.011)		Abnormal β _κ ≠ β _γ
0.22 (11.25)	0.45 (1.017)		
0.45 (14.50)	0.54 (1.036)		
0.90 (16.75)	0.72 (1.069)		

*For comparison of values of K found experimentally.

It can be seen that for compounds marked with asterisks (Table 1), where β_κ = β_γ, a relationship

between $Const_K$ and $Const_\gamma$, can be derived by the equation,

$$Const_K = -1.30 + Const_\gamma \quad (3)$$

A combination of equations (1-3) gives a relation, viz.

$$\log K = -1.30 + Const_\gamma + \beta_\gamma \log C \quad (4)$$

The parallelism between inhibition coefficient K and surface activity $\Delta\gamma$ and also equality of the values of β_K and β_γ , points out the possibility of calculating from electrocapillary data, inhibition coefficients for these aliphatic polyhydric alcohols from equation (4) (Table 2, columns 2-4).

The charge on the Hg surface (qM) in contact with experimental solutions at each potential was

Fig. 3. Dependence of the mercury electrode charge on the potential in $1N H_2SO_4$ solution with different additions of (A) propylene glycol and (B) tetramethylene glycol. Curves for two concentrations only, along with the curve for the base solution have been shown; curves for 1,3-butylene glycol were found to follow the same trend.

obtained by differentiation of electrocapillary curves with respect to potential and are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The surface excess, Γ is proportional to $-\delta\gamma/\log C$, if the activity coefficient of the

Fig. 4. Dependence of the mercury electrode charge on the potential in $1N H_2SO_4$ solution with different additions of (C) ethylene glycol and (D) glycerol. Curves for two concentrations only, along with the curve for the base solution have been shown; curves for rest of the polyols were found to follow the same trend.

alcohol can be assumed constant over concentration range studied. The surface excess values of some alcohols on Hg surface in $1N H_2SO_4$ solution at each potential were obtained from a plot of γ against $\log C$. The variation of surface excess, Γ as a function of surface charge, qM at a few concentrations of some polyhydric alcohols are given in Fig. 5.

Results and Discussion

Polyhydric alcohols under study can be divided into two classes with respect to their electrocapillary characteristics : (i) propylene glycol, 1,3-butylene

glycol and tetramethylene glycol function as polar surface active cation (Fig. 1) and (ii) ethylene glycol, glycerol, erythritol, mannitol and sorbitol function as molecular non-polar organic compound

Fig 5 Variation of adsorption of inhibitors with charge on the mercury electrode in 1N H_2SO_4 solution with different additions of (1A and 1B) ethylene glycol and (2A and 2B) 1,3-butylene glycol (concentration stated on the figure).

(Fig. 2). The adsorption on the negative branch increases in the order, ethylene glycol < glycerol < erythritol < mannitol < sorbitol, which indicates that similar to hydrocarbons and aliphatic alcohols⁷, the horizontal orientation is also characteristic of aliphatic compounds with two or more functional groups. The anomalous positions of propylene glycol, 1,3-butylene glycol and tetramethylene glycol may be due to strong interaction of the electron repelling alkyl groups of these molecules with the negatively charged mercury surface.

It can be seen that qM vs E curves (Fig. 3) for propylene glycol, 1,3-butylene glycol and tetramethylene glycol follow the same trend as observed in the case of monohydric aliphatic alcohols⁷. The curves (Fig. 4) for the remaining alcohols, however, differ at the far anodic sides where curves for solutions do not coincide with the curve for 1N H_2SO_4 solution, indicating lack of progressive desorption at higher positive potential values. It can be seen that qM vs E curves for polyhydric alcohols at various concentrations intersect one another at different potentials, negative to the e.c.m. and at different negative charges, indicating maximum adsorption of these compounds at these values of potential and charge.

The Γ vs qM plots (Fig. 5) of the polyhydric alcohols follow the same general pattern as observed in the case of monohydric alcohols⁷, with an exception in ethylene glycol where the maximum in Γ occurs at e.c.m. of the base electrolyte. The γ vs E and Γ vs qM plots also show that ethylene glycol is equally adsorbed on both branches of the e.c.c., and this suggests its predominant molecular nature.

It may be noted from the present study of the polyhydric alcohols that in the concentration range

1.995–3.162 M, the adsorbability has the following sequence, tetramethylene glycol > 1,3-butylene glycol > propylene glycol > glycerol > ethylene glycol. The order of inhibition effect also runs parallel to the above sequence with only exception between glycerol and propylene glycol.

In the case of polyols (sl. nos. 6 to 8, Table 1), there is a parallel increase of corrosion inhibition and adsorption in the concentration range (0.5012–1.0 M) studied (Table 2); and these properties change in the following sequence, sorbitol > mannitol > erythritol. This is, however, expected from the point of view of their structure, and hence their covering power. A comparison of the adsorbability between monohydric⁷ and polyhydric alcohols shows the following sequence: *N*-butanol > isobutanol > *N*-propanol > isopropanol > tetramethylene glycol > 1,3-butylene glycol > ethanol > propylene glycol > glycerol > ethylene glycol > methanol.

From the above observations, the following conclusions may be made. (i) Both adsorption and hence efficiency in general, increases from secondary to primary compounds. This is, however, expected since aliphatic monohydric alcohols, in general, being more polar than the polyhydric alcohols, should show better adsorptive power and hence, more parallel orientation leading to relatively higher coverage and better inhibition efficiency than the polyols. Methanol seems to be an exception, but this may be due to its vertical orientation resulting from the presence of only one carbon atom in the hydrocarbon skeleton. (ii) Higher inhibitive effect of glycerol over propylene glycol against lower adsorption of the former over latter may be due to strong tendency of complex formation of glycerol⁸ and its pronounced horizontal orientation⁹. (iii) Considering both +I effect of alkyl group and the area of the molecule effective on the surface of the metal, assuming parallel orientation, polyols (sl. nos. 2–4, Table 1) should function as stronger dipole having greater adsorbability and hence, inhibitive property, and are expected to behave in an identical way, which is evident from equality in the values of β_x and β_y (Table 1). The remaining polyols are expected to possess weaker dipole property due to non-existence of substituent groups in the molecule, and therefore, would show a property of weaker electrostatic interaction resulting in an orientation more perpendicular than the parallel one to the metal surface, and thus covering lesser area. It would probably be impossible to obtain necessary amount of adsorption required for good protection because of relatively weak surface forces. In the opinion of Iofa¹⁰, the substances of the non-ionic type are not adsorbed on the iron surface and they have an almost non-existent inhibitive action in acid medium. (iv) The anomalous behaviour of some polyhydric alcohols (sl. nos. 1, 5–8, Table 1) may be due to weak electrostatic interaction resulting from feeble dipolar nature of these molecules.

In conclusion, it may be said that validity of the phi-potential theory depends on (i) reliability of $E_{q=0}$ values¹¹⁻¹⁴, (ii) reliability of the corrosion potential values of the metal under different experimental conditions¹⁵⁻¹⁷, and (iii) the specificity¹⁸⁻²⁰ of the organic inhibitors having varying functional groups leading to adsorption by forces other than electrostatic in nature.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Director, Central Mechanical Engineering Research Institute, Durgapur, and the Principal, Regional Engineering College, Durgapur, for encouragement and permission to publish this paper.

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